

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART I. SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS WITH *o*-CHLOROBENZOIC ACID

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Thorium is precipitated quantitatively by *o*-chlorobenzoic acid from solutions of p_H 2.8 and the above separation from rare earths may be accomplished by a single precipitation from solutions just neutral to Congo red; U, Ni Co, Al and Pb in moderate amounts do not interfere.

Several methods are available for the estimation of thorium, but its separation from the associated cerite earths in monazite is still a problem of some complexity. For the effective removal of the rare earths all reagents require a double precipitation. The following procedure with *o*-chlorobenzoic acid will be of interest both on account of its simplicity and effectiveness. Working with artificial mixtures of thoria and ceria it has been noticed that a sharp separation of thorium results by a single precipitation even in the presence of a ten-fold excess of ceria. When it is taken into account that on the average the ratio of ThO_2 to R_2O_3 is 1 : 12 (and in Indian monazite particularly this ratio is not more than 1 : 8), the advantage offered by this reagent in the recovery of thorium from monazite becomes more apparent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation.—A stock solution of pure thorium nitrate was prepared and estimated with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196). 10 ml. of the solution gave 0.0748 g. of ThO_2 . The same was determined with *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, by precipitating with 0.75 g. of the reagent in boiling solution and igniting the precipitate found 0.0749 g. in excellent agreement with the standard procedure.

Separation.—In as much as separation from other rare earths rests on preferential precipitation under controlled p_H , the precipitation of thorium under different conditions of p_H was investigated. It was noticed that the precipitation of thorium was not complete when the p_H was lower than 2.8, and at p_H 3.8 other rare earths started to precipitate. A convenient p_H range thus appeared to lie between 2.8 and 3.8, a condition that was easily realised by making the liquid just neutral to Congo red.

Procedure.—To the mixed solution containing not more than 0.150 g. of thoria and 1.5 g. of ceria add a few drops of Congo red and diluted ammonia dropwise until the liquid just reacts neutral. Dilute to 100 ml. and boil. Add with continuous stirring 0.75 g. of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid in 75 ml. of boiling water. Continue to boil for 3 minutes and set aside for 30 minutes. Collect the white flocculent precipitate on an 11 cm. Whatman No. 41 filter, wash first with 0.05% solution of the acid and finally with water. Ignite and weigh as ThO_2 .

Results obtained with this procedure on thoria-ceria mixtures as well as other common elements are shown in Table I. The nitrates added are calculated to oxides.

TABLE I

Separation of thorium from the cerite earths.

(A). Amount of ThO ₂ taken = 0.1496 g.			(B). Amount of ThO ₂ taken = 0.0748 g.			
R ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ found.	Difference.	Admixture.	Quantity.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Difference.
0.1200 g.	0.1496 g.	0 g.	R ₂ O ₃	0.1200 g.	0.0747 g.	-0.0001 g.
0.2400	0.1498	+0.0002	"	0.2400	0.0748	-0.0000
0.6000	0.1494	-0.0002	"	0.6000	0.0747	-0.0001
1.2000	0.1496	0	"	1.2000	0.0749	+0.0001
1.4000	0.1492	-0.0004	U ₃ O ₈	0.1200	0.0746	-0.0002
			"	0.2400	0.0748	+0.0000
			NiO	0.1000	0.0747	-0.0001
			CoO	0.1000	0.0746	-0.0002
			Al ₂ O ₃	0.1000	0.0748	+0.0000
			PbO	0.1000	0.0749	+0.0001

Copper, titanium, iron and cerium (quadrivalent) interfere in the precipitation of thorium. Other elements have not been investigated nor are they likely to occur with this element.

Composition of the Precipitate.—From ignition tests on thorium chlorobenzoate it appears that each thorium ion is associated with three molecules of the acid besides four molecules of water. This indicates the presence of a hydroxyl group. The composition is subject to slight variations and therefore direct weighing of the precipitate is ruled out.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—Accurately weighed quantities of Travancore monazite were digested with 3 to 4 times its weight of concentrated sulphuric acid for 4 hours at 200°-250°. The mass was extracted with ice cold water. The residue which was small consisted entirely of silica, titania and possibly zirconia. The oxalates of thorium and rare earths were precipitated twice with oxalic acid. The final oxalate precipitate, which was free from phosphoric acid, was dissolved in fuming nitric acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and the thorium was estimated with *o*-chlorobenzoic acid according to the procedure detailed above, as also with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid after a double precipitation.

<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.		<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid.	
Sample.	ThO ₂ (g.).	Sample.	ThO ₂ (g.).
1.2540 g.	8.98%	1.3460 g.	9.03%
1.0240	9.00	1.0650	9.00
	Av. 8.99%	1.2742	9.02
		Av. 9.02%	